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Research Article

A Comparative study of the Attitude of Hindu and Muslim Women, their Educational Level and Social change in Sitamarhi District

Amit Anand¹**Dr Masood Alam Khan²**

¹Research Scholars in
Education Lalit Narayan
Mithila University,
Darbhanga Bihar
India

²Associate Professor &
H.O.D Education
Department
Dr. Zakir Hussain
Teachers Training College
Laheriasarai, Darbhanga
India

Correspondence
Email:
amitanand0011@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Education is an important factor in any society, with the help of which both the direction and condition of the society change. In ancient India, traditional education was imparted through religious institutions. In the Vedic period, the status of women was very good and high, women were able to work side-by-side with their husbands and could decide for their future life. She had the right over the property of her father and husband. The Swayamvar system was the strong foundation of the social status of women. Women were equal to men in the intellectual field. Lopamudra, the wife of sage Agastya, was the author of Vedic hymns. Maitreyi used to discuss the problems of philosophy with her husband. Mundan Mishra's wife Mandavi had even defeated Adi Shankaracharya in a debate. The queen of Jhansi, Laxmibai gained fame as a heroine Begum Hazrat Mahal, Razia Sultana, and Ahilyabai as an administrator, the whole society is familiar with Noorjahan's administration. Rama's companion Sita, Krishna's beloved Radha, and Meerabai's Spiritual Singing and becoming one with Krishna reveals the form of women's primal power. But during the British Rule, Western Education was introduced in India, which had a unique effect on both Hindu and Muslim women. As a result of the change in their attitude, the women's society took a new turn. In Independent India, the decentralization of power in the fields of politics, the abundant reservation given to women, and the facility of education turned the game. The changed perspective of Indian society and the increasing steps of modernization have changed the lives of women in many roles and social relations. Both Hindu and Muslim women are no longer confined to their families but are playing active roles outside the home for economic gain and personal goals. Educated Women have brought a change in the traditional outlook by joining many jobs and are playing an influential role for themselves and their families and society. As a result of increasing steps of social change, the spread of education political modernization, many types of changes are seen in Indian society. Sitamarhi district is the birthplace of Maa Janki, where the birth anniversary of Maa Sita is celebrated with great respect, even today Hindu women cannot get the respect that they deserve. The condition of Muslim women is even more pitiable, they are limited to their own families their contribution to society is negligible. The reason behind all this is their low education level and low attitude which is not connecting them with modern social change. A logical analysis of all such things and a complete conclusion will be tried in the research paper presented.

Keywords: Attitudes, Social change, Education level, Sitamarhi District, Decentralization

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INTRODUCTION

In modern times, the spread of education is happening at a rapid pace, and as a result, the pace of social change is also fast in the present period. In any society, when there is a change in social values, ideologies, institutions, social roles, patterns of interaction, etc. then we name this social change. Change is the eternal law of nature and life. Social change is also a universal truth. This change takes place in the line of Indian Hindu and Muslim women as per their environmental conditions. There are many factors of socio-economic, educational, cultural, and political fundamentals. At present, different levels of education have not only played a role in social change but have also accelerated the pace of social change. Especially the change in the psychological and social thought currents of women is visible in its effective form. In light of the new education policy, the leading role of today's teacher is to make the subject matter of this research paper present the explanation effectively. People of different religions, communities, and castes have been living in India. They have been expressing their attitude in different languages. They have different ideologies, life values, and cultures, yet there is uniformity and unity in diversity. Hindus and Muslims are major communities living in India for centuries. Comparatively, the pace of social change in Hindu society has been more rapid than that of Muslim society. A lot of changes have been taking place in their social, educational, economic, and cultural fields. In comparison, the transformation of the Muslim community did not take place at the speed that was expected. The main reason for this has been their indifference towards education. The Muslim community, until recently, has been placing more emphasis on religious education received from Maktabas and Madrassas, which have been less concerned with modernity. The Indian constitution has provided equal civil facilities to both the people of the society, yet the Muslim society seems to have lagged behind.

India has been a male-dominated country since time immemorial, the responsibility of the family has been a major challenge before women's participation. The patriarchy of Muslim society has fixed the workplace of women within the four walls of the house. The size of the family of Muslim women is generally found to be large. She gives preference to joint family and her family responsibilities are also more than the women of Hindu society. In such a situation, Muslim women were left behind in thinking in the direction of social and political responsibilities, due to spending most of their time in the discharge of family responsibilities, despite having the ability and capability. Women play a central role in any family. It is the responsibility of the women to nurture the children and provide them with proper manners. That's why it is said that a woman being fully educated is like making a whole family educated. At present in the era of rapid social change, women seem to be most affected. This change appears to be reflected especially in their attitude, ideology, and outlook, so we can say that the effect of women's attitude is sufficiently clearly reflected in society. Changes in the world of women have attracted the attention of sociologists and educationists and teachers have started research work in the light of these facts.

A lot of research work has been done and is being done on various social, economic, and educational problems related to women's education and attitude, to what extent the attitudes of two different religious Hindu and Muslim women are different towards, the various changes happening in the society. There are very few research studies on how much equality is there, how aware they are about these changes what has been the impact of the new education policy on their attitudes or what is the role of education and teachers in this. Therefore this research problem has been chosen to answer these questions.

Literature Review

Pathan, N.M (1986) while presenting his research paper on the educational backwardness of Muslim women said that Muslim women are not educationally strong. The women of the rural society wanted to get their children married at an early age. She hesitated to give more education to her children and did not want to send them out of the house. In the women of rural areas, along with the economic reasons, the effect of social reasons was also found.

Fatima (1989) researched the women of Bangalore city and concluded that education has improved the status of women. She is now fighting the social evils in a good way and getting employment. To get an education she is educated and is also educating her children.

Vasuki (1990) while researching women's attitudes towards education, found that women of all different classes are quite aware of education. They want to make, their place in society by getting alms.

Aggarwal (1992) studied the impact of education on the social and cultural modernization of Hindu and Muslim women and pointed out that education played an important role in changing the ideologies of femininity. This made a serious impact on the customs and traditions, which affected both Hindu and Muslim women. He has not seen any effect of age on the Conservative thinking of Muslim women. Modern Education.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the proposed research work is to study the effect of revolution and progress in education due to social change in present times on Hindu and Muslim Women. Following are some of the major dimensions on which the proposed research paper will highlight:-

- To study the attitude of Hindu women and Muslim women towards social change.
- To study the difference in attitude of Hindu and Muslim Women towards social change.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this, research paper descriptive research design has been used. The information/data related to the subject of the research paper has been obtained from secondary sources and their analytical analysis has been done.

RESEARCH TOOLS

In the proposed study, a comparative study of Hindu and Muslim women's attitudes towards social change concerning their educational level will be done But due to the non-existence of any instrument on this subject, a social change attitude scale will also have to be constructed which will be based on Likert Method. The dimensions of social change towards which efforts will be made to know the attitude of women in this scale are as follows.

- Small Family
- Child marriage, widow marriage and intercaste marriage
- Religious Tolerance
- Educational Status of women
- Freedom of Job / Business for women
- Participation in Politics
- Women have the right to higher education
- Her role in sports, literature and theater.

HYPOTHESIS OF RESEARCH

In the context of the above objectives of the research work and research analysis, the concept of the proposed research management can be kept in the following forms:-

- There is a significant relationship between Hindu Women's attitude towards social change and their educational level.
- There is a significant relationship between Muslim women's attitude towards social change and their educational level.
- There is no significant relationship between Hindu and Muslim women's attitudes towards social change and their educational

level. Keeping these causes and consequences in mind, due research and testing is the basis for its treatment.

DELIMITATION OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

Based on the above reference and practicality, this research study will be delimited as follows:-

- Only Hindu and Muslim women residing in Sitamarhi district will be selected for the present research work.
- In this study Hindu and Muslim women at different educational levels such as illiterate, low-level educated women (8th Standard), medium-level educated women (12th Standard), and high-level educated (Graduate and above) Hindu and Muslim women are involved in social change, what is the attitude towards is to be studied.

COLLECTION OF DATA

100 highly educated and medium-educated Hindu and 100 Muslim women living in Sitamarhi district were personally contacted for the compilation of data and they were informed about the purpose of the research. After that they were given an attitude scale and asked to put a tick in front of any one of the brackets, strongly agree, unsure, disagree, strongly disagree made in front of the statements given in it. Less educated and illiterate women have also been included in this study, so data has been collected for these women using the interview method.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table:-01 Profile of Respondents Based on Religion

Religion	Respondents	Percentage
Hindu women	112	56
Muslim women	88	40
Total	200	100

Table- Profile of Respondents Based on Education Level

Education level	Respondents	Percentage
Technical Education	16	08
Post graduate	20	10
Graduate	30	15
Intermediate	40	20
Matriculation	44	22
Nun-Matriculation	30	15
Literate	20	10
Total	200	100

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER RESEARCH

It is clear from the result obtained from the study of the data that the social status of Hindu and Muslim women there is a general level of attitude towards change. Women with higher education expressed less attitude and women with less education expressed more attitude. Education is the only influence that equally broadens the outlook of women toward social change. Therefore, the need today is that education should be developed more and more. The same fact has been accepted in the intellectual development of a person as well as its attitudes, beliefs, interests, etc, and broadens its intelligence and thoughts.

This research would be very useful in the future for studies related to Hindu and Muslim women in different walks of life. Their attitude to educational, economic, religious, and social behavior would be points of consideration in the future. There are wide possibilities of research study on the research problem and different researchers based on their interest in their aspects of this useful and interesting problem, Research study can be done by selecting. The present research would prove useful and purposive for researchers in times to come.

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